

Review

BASOSH—A Conceptual Framework and Literature Review on Bodycentric Antenna Systems for Occupational Safety and Health

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Abstract

Occupational safety and health (OSH) is increasingly relying on wearable technologies, yet research on such bodycentric antenna systems remains fragmented across diverse disciplines. This review introduces bodycentric antenna systems for occupational safety and health (BASOSH) as a novel unified framework that explicitly links electromagnetic performance, human–body interaction, and OSH objectives within a single conceptual model. Based on a preliminary scientometric analysis, the existing literature is categorized into four application pillars: (i) monitoring workers' health and safety, (ii) supporting occupational activity, (iii) preventing accidents and mitigating risks, and (iv) rehabilitation and prosthetics. The analysis highlights a lack of integrated design approaches, as most studies address only a subset of the BASOSH framework. To overcome this fragmentation, a parametric design function is proposed, jointly weighting wireless performance, human–body effects, and OSH outcomes, to enable the unified design and comparison of BASOSH. By systematizing a previously scattered research area and establishing a common design language, this work defines BASOSH as a distinct research domain and provides a foundation for the development of personalized and context-aware OSH solutions.

Keywords: antenna systems; BASOSH; bodycentric Internet of Things; epidermal antennas; industrial safety; occupational safety and health; wearable antennas

1. Introduction

Occupational safety and health (OSH) is commonly defined as a science concerned with anticipating, recognizing, evaluating, and controlling hazards that arise in or from the workplace that may affect the health and well-being of workers while also considering the broader impact on surrounding communities and the environment [1]. By its very nature, OSH is a highly interdisciplinary domain that encompasses engineering, medicine, ergonomics, environmental science, sociology, and even rehabilitation, including prosthetics and full recovery of injured workers. Its conceptual roots can be traced back to the 17th century, with French Manufacturer Inspectors [2], and to the 18th century, with the pioneering work of Bernardino Ramazzini, widely regarded as the founder of occupational medicine [3]. In modern times, occupational health and occupational safety have progressively converged into a unified discipline, now broadly referred to as OSH, as formalized by global institutions such as the International Labour Organization (ILO) [1,4].

In parallel with this evolution, recent technological advances have reshaped the way workplace risks are monitored and mitigated. Among these, bodycentric (or bodycentric) antenna systems (BASs) have recently emerged as a key enabling technology for

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continuous and context-aware sensing on the human body. These systems, which enable bodycentric wireless communications [5,6], are designed to operate in close proximity to, on, or even within the human body, accounting for its complex electromagnetic (EM) properties. Their integration with wearable and epidermal electronics has further expanded their applicability, allowing lightweight conformal devices to seamlessly interface with the human body [7]. It is interesting to note that OSH applications were envisioned as soon as bodycentric electromagnetism was systematized [8], foreseeing the intrinsic connection between the physical layer and the actual uses analyzed in this work.

In recent years, the paradigm of the bodycentric Internet of Things (B-IoT) has also been developed to describe interconnected ecosystems of body-worn and body-embedded devices capable of processing and communicating physiological and environmental data in real time [9,10]. This paradigm aligns naturally with the increasing demand for personalized and adaptive approaches to OSH, where monitoring solutions must account for individual variability in exposure, physiology, characteristics, and behavior. In this context, a growing body of literature has explored the application of bodycentric antennas to occupational environments, demonstrating their potential to monitor hazardous exposures, enable finer worker localization and management, and support assistive and rehabilitative technologies [11,12]. However, these contributions remain fragmented across disciplines (antenna design, telecommunication systems, medical reports, etc.), and overall they still lack a unifying conceptual framework and rarely consider cross-domain challenges. This fragmentation reveals a fundamental constraint: *in these systems, EM performance, human–body interaction, and OSH requirements are inherently coupled and cannot be independently designed or optimized*. This coupling defines a core research problem for the field and requires integration within a unitary framework.

Existing paradigms such as B-IoT and industrial safety frameworks address only subsets of the BASOSH problem. B-IoT primarily focuses on communication and sensing aspects, often neglecting the explicit modeling of occupational risks and their consequences. Conversely, industrial safety methodologies focus on risk assessment and mitigation but typically treat the underlying sensing and communication systems as black boxes. In order to address this gap in the scientific knowledge, the present review introduces and formalizes the concept of bodycentric antenna systems for occupational safety and health (BASOSH), building upon prior foundational work that preliminarily presented the idea to the academic community [13]. BASOSH are here formalized as integrated systems that leverage bodycentric antennas as core components for sensing and/or communicating in occupational contexts. The objective of this review is therefore twofold: first, to consolidate the existing knowledge spanning bodycentric antennas, wearable electronics, and OSH applications; second, to establish BASOSH as a distinct and strategically relevant research domain, outlining its unique key challenge. In the following pages, accordingly, the BASOSH framework is introduced and used to critically survey the existing literature and, in the end, opportunities and open issues are discussed while a holistic approach to design and evaluation is proposed through a high-level function.

2. BASOSH: Definition and Application

2.1. Technical Background: Bodycentric Antenna Systems

In the BASOSH framework, antenna systems (ASs) cannot be considered as standalone radiating elements but must be interpreted as components whose performance is intrinsically shaped by the human body and the occupational scenario. BASs represent the enabling technological layer of BASOSH. They can be broadly categorized according to their placement in relation to the human body [6,8]. On-body antennas include wearable, textile, and epidermal antennas [7]; they enable off-body, on-body, and through-the-body

communications. In general, wearable antennas are antennas that are placed on and fixed to the human body. Textile antennas are integrated into garments, allowing for unobtrusive operation by relying on conductive fabrics, embroidered threads, and flexible substrates, which allow for conformal integration without significantly hindering the worker's movements. Epidermal antennas are adhesive and directly attached to the skin using ultra-thin and stretchable materials using medical-grade plasters like Tegaderm® [14] or materials like Ecoflex® [15]. These antennas ensure minimal invasiveness and high wearability, making them particularly suitable for long-term monitoring applications and scenarios requiring high user acceptance. In-body antennas are more invasive but technologically relevant. They are implantable antennas designed to operate within the human body with through-the-body communications [16]. These systems are typically employed in medical-grade monitoring or prosthetic applications and must satisfy the most stringent requirements in terms of biocompatibility, miniaturization, energy efficiency, and robustness.

The presence of the human body introduces unique EM challenges that characterize BASs. The lossy and heterogeneous nature of biological tissues leads to absorption, detuning, and distortion of the radiation pattern, which are strongly dependent on the intra-user (point of application, posture, health state, and movements) and inter-user (anatomical and sex differences, body mass index, age, and disabilities) variability [7,10,17]. These effects directly impact communication reliability and sensing accuracy, highlighting the need for robust designs capable of operating under highly dynamic conditions typical of real workplaces. In addition to EM performance, safety constraints play a central role, particularly in terms of exposure to EM fields. In order to avoid biological damage, specific absorption rate (SAR) limits impose strict regulations on the power radiated in proximity to the human body and must be considered during both design and deployment phases [18]. Induced electric fields and currents within biological tissue must be contained as well [19]. In BASOSH applications, these constraints are not only regulatory requirements but are also directly related to occupational safety outcomes and system acceptability, as discussed in the following.

The choice of materials and fabrication techniques is another critical dimension of design. Flexible, lightweight, and biocompatible materials must ensure comfort, durability, and compatibility with daily work activities, especially in harsh environments [20]. Recent advances in additive manufacturing and printed electronics have further enabled rapid prototyping and personalization of ASs [21], a capability that is particularly relevant for tailoring devices to specific workers or tasks [13]. Finally, the design methods for BASs directly account for the coupling between wireless performance and human-body interaction during design and evaluation. For example, the nature of the radio link has major effects on B-IoT systems; inter-subject variability can be negligible in long-range links, while intra-user variability becomes predominant due to the different positioning of the body-worn antenna and the wearer's posture [10]. Therefore, the numerical and iterative design methods to be applied (like the numerical-statistical approach [22] or joint design [23]) must be carefully selected after identifying the target scenario, based on a growing body of BAS literature [20,24].

2.2. Definition and Contextual Framework

Based on the sparse literature we analyzed (see Appendix A for technical details on the literature survey), a BASOSH is a specific kind of antenna system wherein the EM performance is intrinsically related to workers and their vocational activities. Applying the system to work-related environments is essential for distinguishing a BASOSH from a generic medical AS and for optimizing its performance under the challenging conditions typical of occupational settings. BASOSH can therefore be formalized as the simultaneous

presence of three essential components: (i) a physical layer involving antennas, (ii) the presence of the human body intrinsically coupled with EM fields, and (iii) an OSH application or issue to be addressed (Figure 1). Consequently, the design space of such systems is jointly constrained by EM performance, human–body interaction, and OSH requirements, with non-separable coupling among these dimensions.

From the preliminary analysis of the literature, the reports are divided into four application pillars: (i) monitoring the health and safety of workers, (ii) supporting occupational activity, (iii) preventing known accidents and mitigating risks, and (iv) rehabilitation and prosthetics. For completeness, the same works are classified from the antenna perspective in Appendix B via comparative tables. Since BASOSH is an emerging research domain, the majority of reports do not focus on the relationships between the three constituting blocks; especially, the work application is sometimes implied, mentioned, or given as the overarching goal justifying the research work. The medical, sports, and rehabilitation fields, in particular, only partially overlap with vocational applications. However, since professional athletes and task-focused rehabilitation are intrinsically related to the OSH domain, a few selected reports are included in the following survey of the literature based on the expected impact for the OSH research community. The bibliographic tables in the following Sections organize the existing literature, while Figure 2 depicts all the BASOSH application fields and their categorization, providing a taxonomy of the wide field of research. As is evident in the following, BASOSH spans across multiple disciplines (electromagnetism, telecommunications, occupational medicine, industrial safety, etc.) and is a recognizable, emerging domain, with a delimited focus and recurring issues that are currently addressed by borrowing techniques from other research areas. In the literature, no contribution simultaneously addresses all three BASOSH dimensions in a formalized way; at the beginning of each survey section, therefore, we use the BASOSH framework to investigate which components of the triad (EM performance, body interaction, and OSH goals) are explicitly addressed or left implicit by the existing works.

The three logical blocks of BASOSH

Intrinsically interrelated

EM physical layer

- Wireless Body Area
- Body-centric antennas (on-body, wearable, epidermal, implanted)

Human body presence

- EM coupling
- Design constraints

Occupational Health and Safety application

- Workers' well-being
- Accident prevention
- Patients' rehabilitation
- Professional athletes

Figure 1. Components constituting a BASOSH.

Figure 2. Taxonomy of the BASOSH applications present in the scientific literature.

3. Monitoring Workers’ Health and Safety

The first application domain concerns monitoring the worker’s health and safety by exploiting wireless sensors (Table 1). It is the most straightforward and developed use of BASOSH, and many prototypes were manufactured and tested. As is evident in the remainder of this section, none of the works in this application pillar quantify the OSH benefit when designing the system, leading to just a partial integration according to the BASOSH framework.

Table 1. Bibliographic table on telemonitoring workers and supporting their activities.

Class of Application	Application	Details	References
Monitoring Workers’ Health and Safety	Enhancing PPE	Workers’ status	[25–31]
		Correct usage	[32–34]
		Hazards detection	[35,36]
(Tele)Monitoring worker	Risk monitoring and identification	PPE integrity	[37]
		Life cycle data	[38]
		Common workplaces	[39–43]
Supporting the Occupational Activity	Localization and access control	Harsh environments	[44–46]
		Sweat monitoring	[47–49]
		Chronic illness	[50]
	Ad hoc communications	On-body sensors	[51–53]
		Context-aware systems	[54–57]
		Near-miss detection	[58,59]
Work efficiency	Localization	[60–64]	
	Risk assessment	[65–67]	
	Work-optimized links	[68–71]	
Additional environmental info.	Disaster management	[72–75]	
	In-clothes antennas	[76–79]	
	Body-UAV links	[22,80,81]	
Additional environmental info.	Working cobots	[82–86]	
	Working robots	[86,87]	
	Workers’ well-being	[88,89]	
Additional environmental info.	Sensorial ultrability	Hazards monitoring	[90–92]
		Sensorial ultrability	[93–95]

3.1. Enhancing Personal Protective Equipment

Personal protective equipment (PPE) is fundamental to preserving OSH, and pervasive sensing technology can provide it with smart capabilities such as checking the worker’s

health and posture, detecting hazards, or examining the integrity and functionality of the PPE itself. Organizational measures regarding the correct usage of PPE without enabling sensing are also crucial and are discussed next in Section 5.4.

Ultra high frequency (UHF) radiofrequency identification (RFID) technology exploits radiowave backscattering and is therefore extremely effective for low-cost and low-maintenance sensorization. Such sensors can, for example, interact with the industrial setting when integrated into protective gloves or belts [31,32] (Figure 3a) and/or monitor whether the PPE itself is still functioning correctly based on its current status [37] (Figure 3b) or even its life cycle data [38]. The correct use of PPE can be monitored by integrated sensors [33,34], and external environmental hazards can be monitored by the PPE itself, which can communicate with an oversight center owing to protocols such as Long-Range (LoRa) [35]. Wearable antennas (especially textile antennas), possibly combined with long-range protocols, are the main enablers of this critical application.

From the reviewed studies, a clear trend emerges toward the integration of low-power and passive wireless technologies into PPE. These solutions enable cost-effective and scalable monitoring of both worker status and equipment integrity, making them particularly attractive for industrial deployment. However, most existing contributions focus primarily on sensing capabilities and communication feasibility while neglecting a quantitative assessment of the actual OSH benefit provided. In particular, the relationship between smart PPE functions and the reduction in occupational risk is rarely evaluated.

3.2. (Tele)Monitoring Workers' Health

For monitoring the workers' health, wireless body-worn sensors for multiple measurands (such as biomarkers, heart rate variability, body temperature, etc.) and/or external factors (noxious substances like toxins and nanomaterials, environmental factors like noise, microclimate, radiation, vibrations, etc.) can be used. In common workplaces like industries or construction sites, meters and devices are naturally different from the specialized ones in harsh environments, which come with unique sets of goals and risk considerations.

In ordinary occupational environments, such as offices, control rooms, and lean manufacturing workplaces, the primary objective of telemonitoring is not immediate hazard detection but rather the long-term assessment of physiological well-being, fatigue, cognitive load, and comfort. For example, Bluetooth low-energy (BLE) devices can integrate photoplethysmography (PPG), skin temperature sensors, and inertial measurement units (IMUs) to remotely assess heart rate, oxygen saturation, posture, and motion levels during daily work activities [39]. Wireless electroencephalography (EEG) can directly measure workers' attention and/or mental workload, for vigilance monitoring or procedure development [41]. A representative example of design for harsh working environments is given by Heurtefeux et al. in [45]: a Zigbee and Wireless fidelity (Wi-Fi) platform is designed to continuously capture inertial and EEG data using low-power communication protocols and adaptive data reduction mechanisms. Indeed, in harsh environments, minimizing the contention of radio channels and energy consumption becomes critical, as the reliability of communications directly impacts the timeliness of anomaly detection. However, the study falls short of linking service outages with risk increases.

Sweat monitoring sensors deserve special mention because of their recent significant advancements and multiple OSH applications [47]. Beyond the psychophysical state of workers, they can also monitor sports activity with benefits for both professional athletes and rehabilitative sports therapy [48]. Epidermal antennas are the preferred technology for this application given that they do not hinder body movement. Lastly, wireless medical devices are also being studied in workplaces to control chronic conditions such as epilepsy, which can pose major OSH challenges [50].

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3. Examples of BAS monitoring workers’ OSH. (a) Protective gloves sensorized via RFID for touch detection (adapted with permission from [32]). (b) Sensorized facemask for moisture detection, showing when it should be replaced due to excessive humidity through the digitalized metric ΔSC (differential sensor code; adapted from [37]). (c) Radar system for automated detection of near-misses, tested in proximity to a railroad (adapted from [58]).

Overall, the literature on workers' health monitoring shows a strong trend toward multimodal sensing systems combining physiological, environmental, behavioral, and organizational data. The integration of BLE, Zigbee, and other low-power protocols enables continuous monitoring with increasing temporal resolution and user acceptance. Nevertheless, the majority of works remain focused on signal acquisition and transmission, without explicitly linking system performance to actionable safety outcomes. Issues such as communication outages, latency, and data reliability are rarely mapped to their actual impact on occupational risk or decision-making processes. The main limitations and challenges for this application are posed by the use of epidermal and even implantable antennas; even if they are widely used in the medical domain, they are rarely investigated for occupational scenarios, leaving a research gap regarding their design and use.

3.3. Risk Monitoring and Identification

The real-time data transmission directly from the worker's wireless body-area network (WBAN) can allow for the identification of new risks through on-body data gathering to detect unknown and synergistic risks. The automated notification of accidents and near-misses (viz., possibly harmful or even deadly events that occurred but did not cause any harm) also allows regulatory governmental bodies to identify dangerous situations that are systematically underrepresented in the industries' self-reports.

Reconfigurable WBANs including a variety of sensors can enable risk monitoring in the workplace. These systems can include a companion app to report events and the use of machine learning (ML) techniques [51]. The next step is enriching information from the worker's body with additional environmental sensing or communication checks to implement more comprehensive context-aware systems for risk monitoring [54,55]. Similarly, it is possible to achieve automatic detection of near-misses; reference [58] describes the deployment of a software-defined radio detection and ranging (software-defined radar; SDRADAR) that monitors the workzone. By collecting radar data and merging them with additional contextual information, it is possible to recognize near-misses, for example, in the case of railroad maintenance (as depicted in Figure 3c). Although the identification of new risks through the gathered data is theoretically possible and it is the main objective of near-miss reporting, no investigation toward this goal has been reported yet.

4. Supporting the Occupational Activity

The OSH goals can also be pursued by implementing different procedures or introducing new devices to support occupational activity (Table 1). As an example, robots can operate alongside workers to reduce the biomechanical workload of line operators. The support of occupational activity is an application pillar of utmost interest for the BASOSH framework, since it includes localization and ad hoc links, wherein the interrelationship between EM, the body, and OSH is oftentimes addressed during the design of the physical layer. However, it is still done partially and on a case-by-case basis, hindering any possible direct comparison between similar works.

4.1. Workers' Localization and Access Control

Workers' localization and access control (which is straightforwardly implemented from tracking) can in principle be coupled with other applications (e.g., telemonitoring) thanks to information such as the received signal strength indicator (RSSI) and unique identification string. Hence, this section is restricted to works explicitly dedicated to one of the two target applications, excluding works comprising multiple uses, such as [44].

Radiolocation has a long history and a wide range of techniques and protocols that can be chosen [96]. In the BASOSH domain, the constraints related to work determine

the possible design choices; therefore, the most utilized wireless technology in the literature is RFID [60,61,63,65], which exploits low-cost body-worn tags, but studies employing BLE [62], Wi-Fi [66], global navigation satellite system (GNSS) [67], or combined light detection and ranging (LiDAR) with ultra-wideband (UWB) technology [64] are also reported. Other protocols are also preferred in harsh work environments, such as LoRa for search-and-rescue (SaR) missions (see next Section 4.2). Location-based risk assessment is a natural extension when contextual information is accessible at the system level, for example, monitoring artificial ventilation in the tunnel near the locations of workers [66]. All of these investigations do not formally consider the design limitations posed by the workzones that carry a risk factor, simply implying them as part of the engineering problem to be avoided altogether. This is a limiting approach in real use-cases, since a significant decrease in risks and harm can be obtained with suboptimal solutions that are ready to be implemented.

4.2. Ad Hoc Communication Links

Occupations in challenging environments, such as mines, forests, or SaR scenarios, easily induce communication disruptions, posing severe risks for such workers. They also constitute propagation scenarios still little-explored due to their occurrence in rare geographical areas (mountain canyons, through-the-snow links, etc.) and high-risk conditions (extreme temperatures, high-mobility radios, etc.). Automation, like the use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), can introduce further complexity in the scenario. Therefore, a growing body of literature is dedicated to characterizing precisely these links, wherein the coupling between the EM fields, the workplace, and the human body cannot be addressed by separating the three logical blocks. Work-optimized links analyze communications in static workplaces such as mines [69,71], railroads [70], and industries [68]. They apply standard radio propagation studies to highly specific occupational scenarios wherein generic standards are not valid. Disaster management works especially focus on high communication quality [72] or specialized antenna design [75]. In-clothes antennas to optimize ad hoc off-body communications are designed by textile integration [76,77] (Figure 4a) and then possibly enriched with dual-polarization [78] or receiver diversity [79]; epidermal antennas are not taken into consideration due to their reduced EM performance, even though their minimal invasiveness could be precious for indoor applications. Off-body links involving UAVs (a.k.a. body-UAV links) are worth a specific mention, as they contextually characterize the movements of the individual and the UAV in peculiar scenarios such as Mediterranean forests [80] or snow-buried transmitters [81]. Radio propagation of body-UAV links is currently modeled through experimental campaigns and still lacks a dedicated theory.

The analysis of ad hoc communication links in challenging occupational environments highlights an increasing effort toward scenario-specific characterization, particularly in mines, forests, and disaster scenarios. Experimental campaigns and empirical modeling approaches are commonly employed to capture the complex propagation conditions. However, these studies typically prioritize communication performance metrics such as path loss, received power, or link reliability, with limited consideration of how these parameters affect operational safety and mission outcomes. Furthermore, the lack of generalized models limits the transferability of results across different occupational scenarios, creating a scattered set of very different and case-specific models.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Examples of applications for supporting the occupational activity. (a) Antenna integrated into protective clothing and numerical evaluation of its SAR (adapted from [76]). (b) Sensorized shirt for monitoring environmental hazards (adapted from [90]).

4.3. Increasing Work Efficiency

Working efficiency can be greatly increased by improving the workers' well-being or introducing an automated workforce alongside workers, i.e., cobots and robots. Reference [97] states that a "collaborative robot (cobot) is a robot that can interact safely in close spatial and temporal proximity with humans on shared tasks, enabled through environment sensing and autonomous decision making". This subsection follows this distinction; consequently, robots for remote operations are included next in Section 5.2.

Grapplers for assembly alongside humans are the most recently investigated cobots [82,83,85]. They usually have a set of pre-programmed movements and are sensorized to react to human activity, for instance, by using a wireless ring for activation [83]. Skulji et al. proposed tracking worker movements via BASs to automatically control the

very movements of the cobot arm [84]. The working robots are designed to be more autonomous: agricultural automated robots can work in the fields and react to the proximity of humans wearing a radiofrequency beacon to avoid accidents [86,87]. Monitoring workers' physical [89] and cognitive well-being [88] is also an effective method to increase job satisfaction and improve work efficiency. All these reports are mainly dedicated to the OSH domain and deprioritize the bodycentric wireless layer.

4.4. Gathering Additional Environmental Information

BASs can also return to the user additional environmental information that would otherwise be inaccessible, so as to empower new work tasks and procedures, increasing efficiency beyond the known risk to be monitored (included previously in Section 3.3). Body-worn sensors can return information on the possible presence of chemical gasses [91,92] and physical hazards such as extreme temperatures [90] (Figure 4b). Thanks to sensorial ultrability systems (i.e., systems that return to the user an additional artificial sense [95]), workers can even perform novel jobs by sensing differences in quantities such as magnetic fields [94] or dielectric permittivity [93], which is widely studied in the food industry for assessing food quality and preservation [98]. It is worth noting the deep relationship between sensorial ultrability and the Tactile Internet paradigm [99], which is expected to play a major role in the future industry even if it is currently at the conceptual stage. Thus, providing operators previously inaccessible environmental information can potentially achieve multiple OSH goals, but research on the topic still has a very low technology readiness level (TRL).

5. Preventing Identified Accidents and Mitigating Risks

Technological evolution is increasingly improving virtualization and prediction methods to prevent likely accidents and long-term health consequences (Table 2). Whereas the previous sections focused on health monitoring and enhancing vocational activities, in this application pillar, we focus on (i) virtualization and automation that remove the physical presence of the worker altogether, and (ii) organizational measures that ensure ergonomic and safety compliance. Complementary to the first application pillar, this section primarily focuses on the OSH consequences of the systems, neglecting the wireless layer, resulting again in a partial BASOSH integration.

Table 2. Bibliographic table on preventing accidents, mitigating risks, rehabilitation, and prosthetics.

Class of Application	Application	Details	References
Preventing accidents and mitigating risks	Extended reality	OSH training	[100,101]
		Smart operator	[102,103]
		Workplace design	[104]
	Remote robots	Remote control Context awareness	[82,105–108] [109]
Ergonomics	Ergonomics	Biomechanics	[110–114]
		Movements tracking	[115,116]
		Microclimate	[117]
		Neuroergonomics	[118]
Compliance with safety measures	Compliance with safety measures	Organizational measures	[119–121]
		PPE maintenance	[122]
Rehabilitation and prosthetics	Rehabilitation	Occupational therapy	[123–126]
		Exoskeletons	[127]
	Prosthetics	Prosthesis control	[128–130]

5.1. Extended Reality

Extended reality (XR) is an umbrella term that encompasses augmented (AR), mixed (MR) and virtual reality (VR). According to [131], AR allows the worker to see the world together with virtual objects, MR creates a space where real and virtual objects influence each other, and VR is an immersive technology to interact with computer-generated three-dimensional environments. It is evident that XR can significantly enhance the work experience and will be integrated into future workflows.

The most immediate application is the use of WBANs with sensors and gloves for VR-based OSH training in dangerous vocations such as roadside [100] (Figure 5a) and live-line [101] operations. Beyond technological challenges and despite promising results, VR for OSH training remains a highly debated topic, with multifaceted issues (ranging from high costs to lack of digital content and social acceptance) yet to be addressed [132]. Empowering workers during their activities according to the “smart operator” model was proposed by using VR to enhance agile working [102] or AR to interact with machines through digital twins [103]. VR was also tested for designing cobot workspaces by programming the expected cobot’s movements [104] (Figure 5b). The recent review on VR applications for designing workspaces is worth mentioning [133] even if it has a tangential focus w.r.t. the present article as the wireless layer is taken as given. All reports in this research area are currently trying to quantify the benefits of this very recent approach and show high potential for innovation, neglecting again the overall system optimization.

5.2. Robots for Remote Operations

Unlike cobots and robots designed to operate side by side with humans, teleoperated robots can shield workers from harm thanks to remote operations and contextual awareness. Electromyography (EMG) control can be used to control robotic arms remotely; ref. [82,105,107] exploit BLE wearables to pilot a single arm, while Wang et al. [108] consider a dual-arm robot capable of automatically avoiding self-collision. In recent years, 3D printing is also being investigated for producing these robots, paving the way for wide adoption [106]. Larger system architectures connecting such robots with context-aware wireless networks (involving sensors and possibly workers’ WBANs) have been proposed [109], but no implementation has yet reached relevant development or deployment in actual OSH scenarios.

5.3. Biomechanical and Ergonomic Assessment

Ergonomics concerns the understanding of interactions among humans and other elements of a system to optimize both human well-being and overall system performance [134]. It is fundamental for OSH, encompassing biomechanical (mainly for improved comfort, stress reduction, and prevention of musculoskeletal diseases) and microclimatic assessments (concerning the exchange of heat in the worker’s proximity).

The most commonly used methods for biomechanical risk evaluation currently utilize direct observation and/or video recordings [135]. Wireless IMUs can allow for more precise measurements on-site directly during work activity [114], optionally enriched with EMG data [110,112,113] and even ML techniques [111]. This first set of studies uses standard wireless sensors and focuses on OSH applications. Another set of studies focuses on the optimization of the wireless layer for movement tracking without being directly entangled in biomechanical assessments [115,116], providing the complementary viewpoint of the previous set. In the literature, a complete analysis of both the design of the bodycentric system and its consequences on the precision of biomechanical risk evaluation is still missing. A more holistic approach was used for microclimatic ergonomics; indeed,

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5. Examples of applications for preventing known accidents and mitigating risks. (a) Architecture of a VR environment for OSH training (see also [100]). (b) Effectiveness assessment through VR during the design of a workstation with cobots (adapted from [104]). (c) A WBAN monitoring the correct PPE procedure (adapted from [122]).

in recent work, Li et al. designed a system to predict the microclimate needs of the workers and adjust the air conditioning and ventilation accordingly [117]. Lastly, since BASs including wearable neurotechnologies are a fundamental enabler of neuroergonomics, BASOSH and this emerging research topic are deeply intertwined [136]. Very recently, a wearable system was presented at a conference to track and minimize workplace stress [118], demonstrating the potential of this specific application.

The literature on biomechanical and ergonomic assessment demonstrates a growing adoption of wearable sensor systems for real-time monitoring of worker movements and physiological responses. These approaches enable more precise and context-aware evaluation compared to traditional observational methods. Nonetheless, a clear separation persists between studies focusing on sensing technologies and those addressing ergonomic assessment outcomes. In particular, wireless system design is often treated as a fixed constraint rather than as an active component influencing measurement accuracy and reliability. The effects of the hardware or system design on the ergonomic assessment or improvement have not been investigated yet; instead, the complex human–system relationship investigated by ergonomics requires, by definition, a holistic approach still missing in the corresponding antenna design literature.

5.4. Compliance with Safety Measures

One of the main causes of work accidents and casualties is the lack of compliance with safety measures to mitigate risks, be it organizational measures or PPE compliance. Bodycentric wireless systems can monitor compliance with safety measures in real time, provided that the necessary contextual information is available. For example, lone workers can be the target of specific organizational measures and should be monitored [119], as well as operators exposed to a higher risk of collisions on the job [120,121]. For this application, wireless devices must be strictly integrated with the organizational procedures that are further refined on the basis of the sensorized data available (e.g., keeping a distance from the machines as suggested by the body-worn system). Accordingly, the usage of PPE can be improved even without enhancing the protective gear itself; it is sufficient to communicate wirelessly with an optimal smartphone app to ensure that the user knows and follows the optimal maintenance and wearing steps [122], as illustrated by the filtering facepiece respirator in Figure 5c. It is worth remarking that ref. [122] develops a dedicated communication protocol to achieve robust communications in the specific scenario, implicitly following the unitary framework “wireless communication-body area-OSH goal”. This specific application is technologically mature, and authors are currently testing adoption in real case studies.

6. BASOSH for Rehabilitation and Prosthetics

Rehabilitation and prosthetic applications constitute the least investigated application area of BASOSH, since the third logical block (OSH application) is implied by their generic nature. By strict definition, BASOSH are limited only to occupational therapy for work-related tasks and specialized prostheses for vocational purposes [137,138]. In this work, these BASOSH applications are included anyway for the sake of completeness (Table 2), since, although they have not yet been fully developed, research is quickly converging towards refined therapies aimed at work environments [139] and wireless prostheses [140]. BASOSH addressing these applications can hence be expected to be considered and proposed in the next few years, with the potential to revolutionize current approaches. Even though the reports in this application are few and the BASOSH integration is still missing, the unitary nature of the OSH issue and the bodycentric wireless design is self-evident in the existing literature.

6.1. Rehabilitative BASOSH

Rehabilitation of injured workers is a medical issue strictly related to the OSH domain. Occupational therapy, in particular, by focusing on the execution of specific tasks, can be applied directly to vocational purposes. BASs can therefore be used during occupational therapy to precisely monitor movements [123], check patients even at home during rehabilitation [126], or quantify neural responses [124,125]. Similarly, body-worn sensors can support robotic rehabilitation, as reported by Perego et al. in [127] where the TWINMED sensorized t-shirt transmits (via Bluetooth) electrocardiography (ECG) and EMG data during the use of a lower-limb exoskeleton (Figure 6a). Thanks to the recorded data, rehabilitation outcomes are expected to improve greatly, potentially becoming a standard rehabilitation approach. This rehabilitation research is mainly carried out by physicians and practitioners so that it often fails to integrate the technological perspective (see Appendix B for further details). This lack of integration can be attributed to several structural factors. First, rehabilitation research is often conducted within a medical or clinical framework, where the primary focus is on functional recovery, patient outcomes, and usability, while the underlying wireless and EM aspects are treated as enabling technologies rather than design variables. Second, the devices employed in such studies are typically commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) or pre-designed systems, which limits the possibility of jointly optimizing the antenna performance with the application requirements. Finally, a gap in common design metrics persists, as clinical evaluations rely on physiological and functional indicators, whereas antenna and communication systems are traditionally assessed using wireless performance parameters. As a result, the interaction between the wireless layer and the human body is rarely explicitly modeled in rehabilitation studies. These differences hinder a unified optimization approach and further motivate the need for the integrated BASOSH framework proposed in this work.

Figure 6. Rehabilitative and prosthetic BASOSH. (a) Sensorized shirt used during lower-limb exoskeleton-assisted walking. AI-generated illustrative image (by Microsoft Copilot 365[®]); for a real-world photograph of prototype use, see [141]. (b) The wireless prosthetic control MyoPods (by Open Bionics[®]) compatible with the upper limb prosthesis HeroPRO (by Open Bionics[®]; images adapted with permission from [142] and from [143]).

6.2. Prosthetic BASOSH

By broad definition, prostheses substitute body structures to reintegrate lost biological functions. Wireless EMGs are used to control prostheses in research, refine movements for

better control, holding high promises for fully reintroducing the prosthetized patient into the workforce. As an example, neuroprostheses were designed and tested with a driving simulator to check patient alertness in laboratory settings [128]. Ref. [129] exploits the EMG signal from the sound arm to set the correct response of a myoelectric prosthesis, while a flexible glove is utilized to control an upper limb prosthesis in [130]. However, research on the topic is highly complicated by the relative rarity of patients using comparable prostheses. Perhaps the most relevant result in wireless prosthetic control is currently provided by industrial research; the HeroPRO prosthesis by Open Bionics® can be controlled remotely using the EMG signal recorded and transmitted by MyoPods (Figure 6b). The relationship between these commercial BASs and the OSH domain has not yet been addressed in research, but there is no significant technical barrier hindering this evaluation process, as elaborated on in the following.

7. Opportunities, Challenges, and BASOSH Function

7.1. Cross-Pillar Synthesis and Comparative Analysis

The literature review above highlights the existence of a vital research topic that is still scattered across diversified fields. The fragmentation of the literature is evidenced by the analysis conducted in the previous sections and even the presence of several unspecified details in the body of the literature (see Appendix B for detailed data). Most contributions focus on two components of the BASOSH triad and a significant minority on one component only by mentioning the other two as context. For instance, works on wearable sensing systems typically emphasize EM and communication aspects while treating OSH outcomes qualitatively. Conversely, studies on occupational safety often prioritize risk assessment without explicitly integrating bodycentric wireless design. Even if some authors independently and partially involved OSH directly in the BAS design stage even without an established formalization (e.g., [67,77,80,107,115,117,122,127]), no contribution formally addresses all three dimensions within a unified framework, highlighting the need for the unitary approach.

Table 3 draws a comparison between BASOSH across the four application pillars, reporting the kind of antennas employed, the typical applications, main advantages and limitations. Current BASOSH research heavily relies on wearable antennas, with an emerging presence of epidermal antennas mainly limited by their reduced wireless performance; moreover, implanted antennas have not been integrated into the OSH context yet, and they are still being developed in the medical domain. Even if the different classes of BASOSH are characterized by different strengths, it is evident that the first and the fourth application pillars are primarily limited by device-level issues concerning the development and test of new devices, whereas the second and the third pillars additionally meet system-level constraints that require the use of multi-layer system architectures.

Table 3. Comparative overview of BASOSH based on antenna integration across application pillars.

Antenna	Application Pillar	Typical Applications	Main Advantages	Main Limitations
Wearable	Monitoring workers' health and safety	Physiological measurands and risk monitoring	Integration into garments and PPE; reliable communications	Limited comfort; strong dependence on organizational procedures
	Supporting the occupational activity	Localization, tracking, and communication systems	Robust body-worn platforms; adaptability to multiple scenarios	Multi-component architectures; procedural adaptation
	Preventing identified accidents and mitigating risks	Training, ergonomics, and compliance with safety measures	Efficient prevention strategies; availability of COTS components	System complexity; still limited large-scale industrial adoption
	Rehabilitation and prosthetics	Support to occupational therapy and robotic control	Good rehabilitative outcomes; stable communication links	High costs; need for clinical validation; limited personalization
Epidermal	Monitoring workers' health and safety	Sweat analysis and temperature sensing	Minimal invasiveness; long-term comfort; strong body coupling	Reduced EM performance; high inter- and intra-user variability
	Supporting the occupational activity	Chemical exposure sensing and sensorial ultrability systems	Enabling technology for selected scenarios; high user acceptance	Limited validation in real industrial environments

7.2. Opportunities and Open Challenges

The opportunities arising from establishing such a framework are as numerous as the applications, since the holistic viewpoint can quickly identify scientific gaps and promote advancements in the whole area. For example, there is no technological barrier to prosthetic BASOSH anymore, and OSH studies on patients with wireless prostheses can be conceived and carried out in workplaces to quantify design issues, gained benefits, and residual risks. Another example is given by the role of additive manufacturing for BASOSH, which is still an underinvestigated topic with an emerging research community [13,106,144]. Moreover, by applying the unitary framework, multiple application pillars can be pursued by the same wireless system; for instance, the first and fourth application pillars could converge soon. Indeed, cyber-prostheses were recently defined as prostheses including wireless sensing capabilities to return health data directly from the inside of the human body [145], allowing for monitoring the prosthetic effectiveness and health status of the prosthetized worker.

Naturally, several open challenges remain, including technological and conceptual limitations. On the technological side, we can swiftly recognize the need for biocompatibility for implanted devices, structural durability in harsh environments, and the need for multiple 3D-printing techniques to achieve personalization, flexibility, and functional integration (resolution limitations; potential retention of harmful substances). On the conceptual side, we must address performance conflicts (such as combining metallic components for osteointegration with conductive elements for wireless communication) and the need for tailored metrics for the design of BASOSH (viz., design function directly linking the on-body EM parameters and the OSH goal functions; for instance, weighting communication outages by the expected risk in the specific workzone). In fact, in order to optimize the systems for multiple goals simultaneously, there is a need for system-level electromagnetic design approaches, like joint design (which can be defined as the simultaneous optimization of multiple subsystems [23,146]), co-design (which can be defined as an iterative design method wherein the subsystems are designed in sequence [147,148]), constrained design (wherein the parameters' space is limited by external conditions [149,150]), and numerical–statistical methods (that simulate numerically multiple scenarios to derive statistical analyses [22,151]).

A key critical challenge concerns the interaction between EM waves and the human body, which is complicated by the vocational scenario. BASs must always comply with regulatory limits for human exposure [6,7], which impose constraints on transmitted power and antenna design, and system deployment; occupational exposure is a major issue since it

is prolonged and reiterated. The lossy and heterogeneous nature of biological tissues leads to absorption, detuning, and radiation pattern distortion, which are strongly affected by posture, movement, and inter-user variability [5,9,15,16]. These effects introduce additional uncertainty in communication reliability and sensing accuracy, especially in dynamic occupational and rehabilitative scenarios [10,20,93,127].

Therefore, we can identify three main research gaps deriving directly from the absence of a unitary framework in BASOSH research: (i) a technological gap in manufacturing highly customized antennas (even epidermal or implantable) addressing simultaneously the needs of the OSH applications and the use on or in the human body; (ii) a system-level gap, since BASOSH addressing multiple OSH needs can and should be envisioned to foster widespread adoption; and (iii) a design methodology gap, since the design of the wireless system is linked to the OSH performance only in a qualitative or indicative way. This last research gap is further elaborated on in the next Section 7.3.

7.3. BASOSH Goal Function

Therefore, the case-by-case approach currently employed in the scientific literature has evident limits and should be overcome to foster scientific advancement in the domain. In the author's opinion, the development of unitary metrics and their use in selected case studies for designing bodycentric systems should be the initial step towards the next generation of bodycentric antenna systems for vocational purposes. These metrics for optimizing the systems are here formalized in mathematical terms without loss of generality, in a parametric function form named the "BASOSH goal function"

$$Y_{BASOSH}(F) = w_1\varepsilon(F) + w_2\beta(F) + w_3\omega(F) \quad (1)$$

where Y is the actual BASOSH goal function to be maximized when designing the system, F represents the design parameters to be optimized, $\{w_1, w_2, w_3\}$ is a set of weights, ε is a function of the EM and communication performance, β is a function that accounts for the presence of the human body, and, finally, ω is a function that quantifies OSH constraints and goals. Whereas the BASOSH function is presented here at a general level, its purpose is to provide a unifying design language rather than a prescriptive optimization algorithm, whose instantiation is necessarily application-specific. Some typical factors that can be inserted into (1), like bit error rate (BER) [152], are reported in Table 4.

Table 4. Some typical factors for the three terms of the BASOSH function.

ε	β	ω
Realized radiation gain	SAR	Monitoring accuracy
Impedance matching	Postures	Location-based risk assessment
Radiation efficiency	Inter and intra-user variability	Ergonomic benefit
BER	Application point	Heightened efficiency
PDR	State of health	Specific risk reduction

In practical BASOSH implementations, the design space is further constrained by non-technical factors that must be explicitly considered. Regulatory compliance is a primary requirement, including adherence to SAR limits, which may vary across regions and standards. In addition, worker acceptance plays a critical role, involving aspects such as comfort, usability, and privacy concerns associated with continuous sensing. Finally, cost-effectiveness constraints are essential for industrial deployment, as systems must provide measurable benefits while remaining economically sustainable. These factors are typically treated as external constraints in conventional design approaches, but within the

BASOSH framework they can be explicitly incorporated into the β and ω terms and further reflected in the weighting strategy.

A simplified example can illustrate the usefulness of (1). Let us consider an application of the BASOSH function for a mine SaR scenario [153–155]. Let us assume that two different systems should be compared for actual deployment. Both antenna systems to be compared satisfy all the regulations (including local SAR limits [156] and privacy concerns through anonymization [157]) and meet the project specifications (i.e., cost-effectiveness [158], workers' acceptance and comfort surveys [159,160]), so that the two systems can be practically utilized. The BASOSH function can be instantiated to compare the two systems (F_1, F_2) and choose between them. In this simplified example, ε is the estimated packet delivery ratio (PDR) for transmission in mines [161], β is the equivalent radiation gain derived through a numerical–statistical approach to account for posture variability [22], and ω is the estimated rescue time [162], which is affected by communication latency and the employed localization algorithm. The values of the three terms are normalized to the best value among (F_1, F_2). Consider four possible weighting choices by the evaluator, each corresponding to a weighting vector $\vec{w} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3\}$: \vec{w}_A equally weights the three terms, \vec{w}_B prioritizes the risk reduction, \vec{w}_C focuses on the PDR, and \vec{w}_D maximizes the importance of robustness w.r.t. the envisioned posture. In practical implementations, the weights should be selected based on the risk profile of the application: safety-critical scenarios (e.g., mine search and rescue) require prioritizing the OSH-related term, while communication-driven applications may emphasize wireless performance. The selection of the weights therefore reflects explicit design trade-offs that are typically implicit in conventional approaches. After the selection of weights, standard multi-objective optimization techniques (e.g., Pareto optimization or weighted-sum methods [163]) can be employed to maximize the BASOSH goal function once the weights are selected.

Table 5 reports the combinations of the simplified example, and the Y_{BASOSH} of system-weighting pair achieving the highest goal score is highlighted. System one F_1 is the optimal choice for most functional weighting strategies, whereas F_2 should be selected if the risk reduction is deemed much more important than link reliability and robustness to varying postures because of relatively safe workzones or mostly static work postures. The results are plotted in the three-dimensional design space in Figure 7, showing how the weighting policy affects the design space and the Y_{BASOSH} value. Even if the example is extremely simplified, it shows how two technical solutions can be compared and selected by using the BASOSH function and choosing a weighting strategy. Hence, the BASOSH function here proposed can be utilized as a backbone for comparing different works, regulating, and designing antenna systems based on the weight selection, which by its very nature is context-dependent and makes explicit design choices that are currently still implicit. Hence, the BASOSH function makes possible future research on how to prioritize weights in different scenarios, what optimization algorithm to employ, and what design guidelines should be created and followed. Naturally, this promising research direction needs to grow through future case-by-case instantiation, since the BASOSH function is intended as a tool for analyzing the bodycentric wireless systems for OSH.

Table 5. An example of BASOSH function used to compare two different systems in mine SaR when choosing different functional weighting priorities.

(F, \vec{w}) pair	ε	β	ω	w_1	w_2	w_3	Y_{BASOSH}
(F_1, \vec{w}_A)	1	1	0.7	1/3	1/3	1/3	0.90
(F_2, \vec{w}_A)	0.8	0.7	1	1/3	1/3	1/3	0.83
(F_1, \vec{w}_B)	1	1	0.7	1/4	1/4	1/2	0.85
(F_2, \vec{w}_B)	0.8	0.7	1	1/4	1/4	1/2	0.88
(F_1, \vec{w}_C)	1	1	0.7	1/2	1/4	1/4	0.93
(F_2, \vec{w}_C)	0.8	0.7	1	1/2	1/4	1/4	0.83
(F_1, \vec{w}_D)	1	1	0.7	1/4	1/2	1/4	0.93
(F_2, \vec{w}_D)	0.8	0.7	1	1/4	1/2	1/4	0.80

The BASOSH function can also be used to interpret existing works in the literature. The studies in Sections 3 and 4 focusing exclusively on EM performance correspond to optimizing primarily the ε term, often neglecting the β and ω . Conversely, works centered on OSH like most in Section 5 can be interpreted as prioritizing ω while treating the EM layer as a fixed constraint. Extreme cases leading to failure would be, for instance, exceeding SAR limits ($w_2 = 0$; β ignored) or not considering OSH metrics ($w_3 = 0$; ω ignored); these systems could not be used due to regulatory constraints nor adopted by industry due to the lack of measurable safety benefits, respectively. This perspective highlights how current approaches implicitly adopt partial optimizations of the BASOSH function, reinforcing the need for the explicit three-dimensional design framework this work suggests.

Figure 7. Three-dimensional scatterplot representing the system-weighting pairs and the corresponding value of Y_{BASOSH} . The points representing BASOSH F_1 and F_2 are connected by lines.

8. Conclusions

This review has analyzed the state of the art of bodycentric antenna systems for occupational safety and health, organizing the literature into four application pillars. The analysis reveals that current BASOSH research remains strongly fragmented, with most contributions addressing only a subset of the three core dimensions (electromagnetic performance, human–body interaction, and OSH objectives). From a technological perspective, several key trends emerge. Wearable antenna systems dominate the current landscape, supported by the widespread adoption of low-power wireless technologies (e.g., BLE, RFID, ZigBee, and LoRa) and multimodal sensing platforms. At the same time, epidermal antennas represent an emerging direction, offering improved comfort and body coupling at the

expense of reduced wireless performance. Implantable antennas are still not investigated in the BASOSH domain, even if they are expected to play a crucial role in future systems. A key trend is the increasing complexity both at the device and system levels, with antennas becoming increasingly miniaturized and multi-protocol approaches emerging.

Despite these advancements, significant challenges remain. A technological gap persists in the development of highly customized and application-specific antenna systems, including epidermal and implantable solutions suitable for occupational environments. A system-level gap emerges from the limited exploration of BASOSH architectures capable of addressing multiple OSH objectives simultaneously. Most critically, a design methodology gap is evident, as current approaches rarely establish quantitative links between wireless system performance and OSH outcomes. To address these limitations, this work introduces the BASOSH framework as a unified design paradigm, together with a parametric goal function enabling the joint evaluation of electromagnetic, human–body, and OSH aspects. A simplified example shows how to employ the BASOSH function for evaluating two comparable systems for mine SaR. Looking ahead, the adoption of integrated and quantitative design methodologies has the potential to enable personalized, context-aware, and scalable safety solutions.

Recognizing BASOSH as a research domain and adopting a holistic design approach is both an academic and an applied scientific challenge that involves vital consequences in the near future. If the research community can identify, address, and overcome the multifaceted challenges of this domain, the concept of *personalized OSH*, tailored to the needs of individual workers, will significantly advance and improve working conditions worldwide.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

AR	Augmented reality
AS	Antenna systems
BAS	Bodycentric antenna systems
BASOSH	Bodycentric antenna systems for occupational safety and health
BER	Bit error rate
B-IoT	Bodycentric Internet of Things
BLE	Bluetooth low energy
COTS	Commercial off the shelf
ECG	Electrocardiography
EEG	Electroencephalography
EM	Electromagnetism (or electromagnetic)
EMG	Electromyography
GNSS	Global navigation satellite system
ILO	International Labour Organization
IMU	Inertial measurement unit
LiDAR	Light detection and ranging
LoRa	Long-range
ML	Machine learning
mmWave	Millimeter wave
MR	Mixed reality
OSH	Occupational safety and health
PDR	Packet delivery ratio
PPE	Personal protective equipment
PPG	Photoplethysmography
Radar	Radio detection and ranging
RFID	Radiofrequency identification
RSSI	Received signal strength indicator
SAR	Specific absorption rate
SaR	Search and rescue
SDRADAR	Software-defined radar
TRL	Technology readiness level
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
UHF	Ultra high frequency
UWB	Ultra-wideband
VR	Virtual reality
WBAN	Wireless body-area network
Wi-Fi	Wireless fidelity
XR	Extended reality

Appendix A. Scientometric Investigation and Methodology of the Review

The literature survey was carried out adopting two different approaches. ScientoPy scientometric software [164] was used in the first approach to identify BASOSH applications in the core of the scientific databases Web of Science (WOS) and Scopus. The second approach consisted of scouting Google Scholar to find additional interesting publications for the identified applications. Studies were included if they (i) involved bodycentric antenna systems or wireless devices operating on, near, or within the human body; (ii) addressed, either explicitly or implicitly, an occupational or work-related scenario; and (iii) provided sufficient technical or application details to be analyzed within the BASOSH framework. Both experimental and theoretical contributions were considered, including works from adjacent domains (e.g., sports or rehabilitation) when a clear relevance to occupational contexts could be established. Studies were excluded if they (i) focused solely on generic wireless systems without human–body interaction or possible OSH application; (ii) addressed purely medical applications with no plausible extension to OSH scenarios; (iii) lacked

sufficient technical detail (e.g., missing crucial information on the wireless system—such as on- or off-body placement of the antennas—or application context); or (iv) were not accessible in full text. A structured query was applied to major scientific databases (Scopus and Web of Science), and records were filtered by document type and duplicates removed. The complementary manual search using Google Scholar was conducted to identify relevant works not captured by the initial query. The final selection was obtained through abstract screening followed by full-text evaluation, based on the criteria above. Overall, the review process followed a structured pipeline consisting of database query, record filtering, abstract screening, and full-text evaluation.

Patents (e.g., [165–167]) were not included in the structured literature review. This choice is methodological and reflects the objective of the present work, which is to analyze the scientific development and formalization of the BASOSH concept within peer-reviewed academic literature. Scientific publications provide reproducible methodologies, explicit modeling approaches, and comparable performance metrics, which are necessary for a systematic and critical analysis. Patent literature, while highly relevant for assessing industrial innovation and technology transfer, is considered in this work only as contextual evidence of technological relevance and emerging applications and is therefore not included in the systematic dataset. The discussion of the TRL in this work is qualitative and based on evidence available in the scientific literature, such as the presence of prototypes, experimental validations, and reported applications. It is not intended as a formal or quantitative TRL assessment but rather as an indicative description of the maturity of different application domains.

The databases were last browsed on 18 April 2026, for updated ScientoPy (<https://github.com/jpruiz84/ScientoPy>) processing. In the first approach, the databases were queried using a composite string representing the three logical blocks identifying a BASOSH, as written in Section 2: for the EM physical layer, the block was {"WIRELESS" OR "ANTENNA" OR "RADIOWAVE" OR "WBAN"}; for the human body involvement, keywords were {"WEARABLE" OR "BODY-CENTRIC" OR "BODYCENTRIC" OR "ON-BODY" OR "IMPLANTED" OR "BODY SHADOWING" OR "PROSTHESIS"}; for the OSH application, {"WORKER" OR "WORKPLACE" OR "VOCATION*" OR "OCCUPATION*" OR "SPORT"} was used. The {AND} logical operator connected the three textblocks. Since the BASOSH field of study is strongly variegated and scattered, this approach underrepresents the actual research domain, investigated by the survey through the second approach. However, this restrictive search was selected to identify the presence of the core literature that actually demonstrates the presence of an unnamed field of research here formalized in the BASOSH framework. The first approach omitted all documents that were not journal or conference articles or reviews. Duplicates between databases were also removed. In the end, 1110 records were used for trend analysis (Table A1).

Table A1. ScientoPy processing of the database results.

Database	All Results	Removed by Type	Removed Duplicates
SCOPUS	1079	852	845
Web of Science	422	265	265
Total	1501	1117	1110

Five keywords were selected to analyze historical trends in the restricted set of reports: HEALTH, REHABILITATION, ACCIDENT PREVENTION, SAFETY, and RISK REDUCTION. Although the set cannot fully describe the precise evolution of the BASOSH field, we can state that this research line was born in the early 2000s, focusing first on health monitoring and rehabilitation. Only after 2010 have the aspects related to greater prevention of harm

gained traction, probably fostered by more widespread sensors (Figure A1a). Figure A1b restricts the analysis to the last five years (2021–2025); overall, all BASOSH applications show vitality in the restricted dataset, with {"RISK REDUCTION" + "SAFETY" + "ACCIDENT PREVENTION"} returning promising growth. However, in the absence of a recognized field of research, the scientometric tool used can only provide a qualitative analysis, here useful for setting the literature survey and conceptualization of the area.

Figure A1. Scientometric processing of the retrieved records. (a) Evolution plot with cumulative number of published papers based on the relevant keyword. (b) Plot summarizing the publishing trends during years 2021–2025.

Appendix B. Comparative Summary Tables

Tables 1 and 2 categorize the literature focusing on the OSH application; in this Appendix, the same works are clustered based on the technological perspective. Table A2 and Table A3 include the BASOSH exploiting wearable antennas, whereas Table A4 organizes the systems utilizing epidermal antennas. A set of technologies using different operating frequencies can be observed, mainly Bluetooth and Wi-Fi (2.4000–2.4835 GHz band), UHF RFID (860–960 MHz band), ZigBee (868 MHz and 2.4000–2.4835 GHz bands), and LoRa (868 MHz band). A significant minority of the relevant literature reports only generic details on wireless technology or OSH application (~10% and ~5%, respectively); those reports are labeled as “unspecified”. “Hybrid” systems deploy a combination of wireless technologies, and “Custom” systems either employ proprietary or ad hoc wireless protocols. Interestingly, among the wireless technologies, beyond typical low-power protocols, also millimeter wave (mmWave) and SDRADAR are present.

Table A2. BASOSH based on wearable antennas that use a single wireless technology. Works that only provide generic information on OSH applications are marked as *unspecified*.

Wireless Tech.	OSH Scenario	Application Pillar	References
Bluetooth	Construction	Workers' monitoring Supporting activity	[28,31,33] [62]
	Manufacturing	Workers' monitoring Supporting activity	[41] [89]
	Robotic rehabilitation	Rehabilitation and prosth. Mitigating risks	[127] [104,105,107]
	Healthcare	Workers' monitoring	[9]
	Office	Workers' monitoring	[39]
	Harsh environment	Supporting activity	[90]
	Warehouse	Mitigating risks	[112]
	Occupational therapy Prosthetics	Rehabilitation and prosth. Rehabilitation and prosth.	[123] [128]
Wi-Fi	Manufacturing	Workers' monitoring Supporting activity Mitigating risks	[50] [84] [102]
	Construction	Workers' monitoring	[46]
	Tunnels	Supporting activity	[66]
	Mine Search and rescue	Supporting activity Supporting activity	[69] [75]
UHF RFID	Manufacturing	Workers' monitoring Supporting activity	[32,34] [61,63]
	Construction	Workers' monitoring Mitigating risks	[38] [121]
	Healthcare	Workers' monitoring	[29,37,43]
	Harsh environment	Workers' monitoring	[44]
	Agriculture	Supporting activity	[86,87]
	Warehouse Biomechanical risk	Supporting activity Mitigating risks	[60] [115]
ZigBee	Mine	Workers' monitoring	[26]
	Construction	Workers' monitoring	[56,59]
	Lone worker	Workers' monitoring	[53]
	Harsh environment	Supporting activity	[92]
	Manufacturing	Supporting activity	[83]
LoRa	Search and rescue	Supporting activity	[22,73,74,80,81]
	Unspecified	Workers' monitoring	[35]
IEEE 802.15.4	Ergonomics	Mitigating risks	[116]
	Unspecified	Supporting activity	[79]
mmWave SDRADAR Satellite	Firefighting	Workers' monitoring	[36]
	Railroad	Workers' monitoring	[58]
	Mine	Supporting activity	[67]

Table A3. BASOSH based on wearable antennas and using multiple or custom wireless technologies. Works that do not detail the employed protocol or approach are categorized as *unspecified*.

Wireless Tech.	OSH Scenario	Application Pillar	References
Hybrid	Manufacturing	Workers' monitoring	[42,54,57]
		Supporting activity	[70,82,168]
		Mitigating risks	[103,109,120]
	Construction	Workers' monitoring	[52,55]
		Supporting activity	[65]
	Harsh environment	Workers' monitoring	[45]
	Agriculture	Supporting activity	[64]
	Railroad	Supporting activity	[68]
	Search and rescue	Supporting activity	[72]
OSH training	Mitigating risks	[100]	
Ergonomics	Mitigating risks	[117]	
Lone workers	Mitigating risks	[119]	
Custom	Construction	Workers' monitoring	[25]
	Mine	Supporting activity	[71]
	Manufacturing	Supporting activity	[85]
	Harsh environment	Mitigating risks	[122]
	Occupational therapy	Rehabilitation and prosth.	[124,125]
	Prosthetics	Rehabilitation and prosth.	[129,130]
Unspecified	Manufacturing	Supporting activity	[88]
		Mitigating risks	[106,108,118]
	Search and rescue	Workers' monitoring	[27]
		Supporting activity	[76,77,79]
	Construction	Workers' monitoring	[40]
	Biomechanical risk	Mitigating risks	[110,111,113,114]
	OSH training	Mitigating risks	[101]
Occupational therapy	Rehabilitation and prosth.	[126]	

Table A4. BASOSH based on epidermal antennas.

Wireless Technology	OSH Scenario	Application Pillar	References
UHF RFID	Sports	Workers' monitoring	[48]
	Unspecified	Supporting activity	[93–95]
Inductive	Harsh environment	Workers' monitoring	[49]
Hybrid	Sports	Workers' monitoring	[47]
	Harsh environment	Supporting activity	[91]

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